

MLOps Course – Initial Questionnaire

This questionnaire aims to probe the initial knowledge and expectations of the students attending the MLOps course during the academic year 2022-2023.

The survey is anonymous. The record of the survey responses does not contain any identifying information about the students; analytical results produced from this record may be published only in aggregated form.

* *Indica una domanda obbligatoria*

1. How would you define your experience in Software Engineering? *

(i.e., your experience in designing, implementing, testing, and maintaining complex software solutions)

Please, answer with a number from 1 to 5, where:

- 1 = "Very Poor"
- 2 = "Below Average"
- 3 = "Average"
- 4 = "Above Average"
- 5 = "Excellent".

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

2. How would you define your experience in Machine Learning and Deep Learning? *

(i.e., your experience in building data-driven AI models)

Please, answer with a number from 1 to 5, where:

- 1 = "Very Poor"
- 2 = "Below Average"
- 3 = "Average"
- 4 = "Above Average"
- 5 = "Excellent".

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

3. Think about the project(s) in which you have leveraged ML/DL techniques so far. Which were the related ML/DL applications? *

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

- Image classification
- Object detection
- Pose estimation
- Speech recognition
- Gesture recognition

- Segmentation
- Text classification
- On-device recommendation
- Natural language question answering
- Digit classifier
- Style transfer
- Smart reply
- Super resolution
- Audio classification
- Video classification
- Reinforcement learning
- Optical character recognition
- On-device training
- Altro: _____

4. While working at your previous ML/DL project(s), did you adopt any of the following practices?

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

- Requirements engineering
- Project coordination and communication
- Pre-defined project structure
- Code versioning
- Data versioning
- Experiment tracking
- Energy efficiency assessment
- Code/notebook quality assurance
- Model testing (with assertions)
- Data testing

- API development for model serving
- Containerization (e.g., using Docker)
- Continuous Integration, Continuous Delivery, or Continuous Deployment
- Resource monitoring
- Model performance monitoring
- Altro: _____

5. If you checked any of the options from the question above, please provide some details here (e.g., the technology used to implement the selected practice).

6. What do you expect to learn from this course? *

7. Do you want to leave any further comment before submitting your answers?
